

In search of Tuberculosis drug design : An *in silico* approach to azoimidazolyl derivatives as antagonist for Cytochrome P450

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Abstract : Tuberculosis is a deadly disease and is caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb). Cytochrome P450s (CYPs) in the Mtb genome is playing important physiological role for its growth and survivability. Azole drugs have potent anti-mycobacterial activity and molecular docking studies indicate that CYP inhibition is the major target of the drugs. Out of six structures of CYPs in PDB (CYP51, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP130 and CYP142) CYP121 has shown better binding affinity with fluconazole, an antifungal medicine. In this work we have searched for a series of arylazoimidazole molecules, the structural analogue of fluconazole, those act as antagonist via *in-silico* approach with CYP121. It is calculated that arylazoimidazole ligands have better binding affinity and higher docking score compared to fluconazole and other available azole drugs. Most of the molecules have crossed the druglikeness filter though Lipinski's rule and Ghosh's rule. QSAR calculation has shown that there is positive correlation ($R^2 > 0.5$) among the docking scores and molecular properties of the azole structure analogous. ADMET calculation has also shown that one of the arylazoimidazoles, (*E*)-6-((3-((1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)naphthalen-2-yl)amino)-2*H*-chromen-2-one (Molecular ID-85; Mol. wt., 453.54; docking score, -10.9; log P, 3.928), is best docked and druglikeness passed and crossed the barrier of ADMET filter.

Keywords : *M. tuberculosis*, structure based drug design, arylazoimidazoles, molecular docking, virtual screening, QSAR, ADMET.

Introduction

One third of the World's population has been suffering from tuberculosis¹, caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*M. tuberculosis*, abbreviated Mtb, Fig. 1). The reasons of disease were clarified in 1882 by Robert Koch and the vaccine, Bacillus Calmette-Guerin (BCG) was exposed² by Dr. Albert Calmette and Dr. Camille Guerin, French bacteriologists, in 1906. In view of the drug-resistant TB problem (multidrug resistant tuberculosis, MDR-TB and extensively drug resistant tuberculosis, XDR-TB), there is an urgent need to develop new anti-TB drugs. The bacterial Cytochromes play major role in metabolism in the pathogens; blocking of Cytochrome could result in killing the pathogen³. First line drugs for TB treatment are Rifampicin, Ethambutol, Isoniazid, Pyrazinamide; second line drugs are Kanamycin, Amikacin, Cycloserine, Capreomycin, Ofloxacin, Ethionamide, Streptomycin, *para*-amino salicylic acid and third line drugs are Clofazimine, linezolid, amoxicillin plus clavulanate,

Fig. 1. *M. tuberculosis*, a gram variable filamentous rod with mycolic acid in its cell wall.

imipenem plus cilastatin, clarithromycin⁴. Literature survey reveals that azole drugs (Scheme 1) have potent anti-mycobacterial activity and have CYP-drug interaction

Scheme 1. Some commercially available azole drugs.

history^{5,6}. The CYPs of Mtb enzymes have roles in the synthesis or other biotransformation of the complex mycolipids those are essential for cell-envelope manufacture and integrity of the microbe. Among 20 CYPs the PDB structures of CYP51, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP130 and CYP142 are available. Expression, purification and crystallization of the Mtb-CYP51 proved a much simpler proposition than for its eukaryotic counterparts, allowing clarification of the Mtb-CYP51 structure in complex with the azole drugs⁷. The CYP active site undergoes drug-protein interactions that have specificity for fluconazole and related azole drugs (Scheme 1)⁶. CYP51 and CYP121 were co-crystallized with fluconazole but CYP121 has shown better stability^{8,9}. Recent studies have demonstrated that azole anti-fungal drugs are extremely potent inhibitors of mycobacterial cell growth, with MIC values for the most potent azoles being ≤ 0.1 mg/ml⁶.

Some azole drugs have adverse side effects, liver damage or affecting estrogen levels; azole medicines can cause allergic reactions in many people¹⁰. This has prompted to search for derivatives of known drugs or their neighboring group members who could have lower toxicity and easy to synthesize. Imidazole, one of the bioactive heterocyclic and a member of azole family, is ubiquitous in chemistry and biology. Imidazole is functionalized towards development of target pointed molecules in biology, medicine and material industry. Azo (-N=N-), one of the important functional group, is highly useful in synthetic organic dyes, coloring agents for foods and cosmetics, liquid crystal, organic photoconductor, nonlinear optics, photochromism, pH indicators in analytical chemistry¹¹. Azo dyes are well known for their antiseptic activity and some are useful as chemotherapeutic agents¹².

The pharmacological use of azo compounds originates from the discovery of the antibacterial action of Prontosil on streptococcal infections by Dogmagk¹³. Azo compounds show a variety of biological activities including antibacterial¹⁴, antifungal and antiviral¹⁵ activities.

Our research group is associated for last two decades with the advancement of chemistry of heterocyclic azo compounds and their different metal complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Arylazoimidazole is one such molecule is used to characterize series of coordination complexes¹⁹⁻²¹ their magnetic^{22,23}, photochromic²⁴, liquid crystal properties²⁵ are examined and some of the derivatives show biochemical activities²⁶⁻²⁸. Besides, metal bonded arylazoimidazoles show unusual chemical reactions those are practically impossible in absence of metal ion²⁹⁻³¹. One such reaction is C-N coupling reaction³¹ of pendant naphthyl ring in $[\text{Pd}(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR})\text{Cl}_2]$ ($\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR} = 1\text{-alkyl-2-(naphthyl-}\alpha/\beta\text{-azo)imidazole}$) with Ar-NH_2 to synthesize, $\text{Pd}(\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR-N-Ar})\text{Cl}$, chloro[1-alkyl-2-{(7-imidophenyl)naphthyl- α -azo}imidazole- N,N',N'']palladium(II), from which $\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR-NH-Ar}$ (1-alkyl-2-{(7-imidophenyl)naphthyl- α -azo}imidazole) may be separated by reduction with $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In arylazoimidazole derivatives, imidazole ring is in conjugation with aryl group via azo bond which may reduce the toxicity of azole drug and might be useful in the microbial treatment. $\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR-NH-Ar}$ (imidophenyl-naphthyl-azoimidazole, Scheme 2(b-g)) has structural analogy with $\text{N-}((6,7,8,9\text{-tetrahydro-5H-[1,2,4]-triazolo[4,3-a]zepin-3-yl)methyl)naphthalen-2\text{-amine}$ (Scheme 2h), one of the potent lead molecules of high docking score (Table 1). Both of them have pendant naphthyl ring, bonded via exocyclic-N to form five membered N-heterocycle. This structural similarity has encouraged us to find drug potential activity of $\alpha/\beta\text{-NaiR-NH-Ar}$ via *in-silico* approach

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using drug-protein interaction technique by docking experiment. Since the expense of discovering a new drug in a wet laboratory is very high and time consuming; it will be frugal and time saving initiative to first make the blue print of drug in an *in silico* laboratory. Herein, we have evaluated the biomedical activity by *in silico* techniques using series of imido(phenyl/naphthyl)-aryl-azo-imidazole derivatives (Scheme 2(a-g)) and the results have been compared with lead molecules and known drugs.

Experimental

Methodology :

The first objective for structure based drug design is target identification. It was done using literature survey for newly identified and validated targets for Mtb pathogen and for the present work we selected bacterial Cytochrome P450 as target for designing new drugs. Validation is a crucial step in the drug discovery process. Most

R = H, -Me, -OMe, -Cl, -NO₂, -CHO, -COOH; R' = H, -Me, -Et, -CH₂Ph

Scheme 2. Imido(phenyl/naphthyl)-aryl-azo-imidazole derivatives (a)-(g) and N-((6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]azepin-3-yl)methyl)naphthalen-2-amine (h) used in this work.

These analogues are then docked to the CYP121. The analogues have also passed through the drug like, ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion) and toxicity properties. Most of the analogues passed all the filters. The tight binding of fluconazole with CYP121^{8,9} insist us to design Mtb drugs with azole compounds.

drugs are inhibitors those blocks the action of a particular target protein. The Cytochromes P450 enzymes are largest in number ever found in bacterial genome. Of the twenty Mtb-CYP enzymes, only CYP51, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP130 and CYP142 (Fig. 2) have been structurally and biochemically characterized. These

Fig. 2. Cytochrome P450s structure of CYP51, CYP130, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP142 is represented by 2(a), 2(b), 2(c), 2(d), 2(e), 2(f) respectively. Structures are represented by solid ribbon model, coiled ribbons represents alpha helix, flat structures represents beta sheet and thin connecting lines represents loop, red dots represents water molecules, coloured according to secondary structure, ligands (azole drugs) and Hem represented by ball and stick.

enzymes are likely to be involved in the synthesis and introversion of membrane lipid and sterols, important to cellular integrity. Cytochromes P450 enzymes also found in human body but their functions are different; by target validation it could be assured that the potential drug should not harm human cell by any means³². To identify the homology and relationship amongst all known 20 Cytochromes, sequence comparison was performed using multiple sequence alignment in Clustal W2 and BLAST^{33,34}.

Clustal W is a general program used for multiple sequence alignment of protein and nucleotide (DNA, RNA). In this program we found out similarities between different sequence of same organism or different organism. It uses Needleman-Wunsch algorithm. The degree of similarities is illustrated by the alignment with a symbol. Evolutionary relationship can be seen through viewing phylograms. Six of the twenty *M. tuberculosis* (H37Rv) CYPs have been structurally and functionally characterized to date according to protein data bank (<http://www.rcsb.org/pdb/home/home.do>). They are CYP51, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP130 and CYP142. Clustal W2 (Phylogenetic analysis) of twenty *M. tuberculosis* CYP amino acid sequences result had shown that their roles had been difficult to assign because of a distinct lack of sequence similarity with other CYPs of known function, and owing to extensive divergence within the *M. tuberculosis* CYP group itself^{3,6}.

Basic Local Alignment Search Tool, or BLAST, is an algorithm for comparing primary biological sequence information³³ such as the amino-acid sequences of different proteins or the nucleotides of DNA sequences. A BLAST search enables to compare a query sequence with a library or database of sequences, and identify library sequences that resemble the query sequence above a certain threshold. The main idea of BLAST is that there are often high-scoring segment pairs (HSP) contained in a statistically significant alignment. BLAST searches for high scoring sequence alignments between the query sequences and sequences in the database using a heuristic approach

that approximates the Smith-Waterman algorithm (Supplementary Material Table S1 and Fig. S1). The BLAST result showed that 2ij7 had maximum identity of 100% (Total score, 800) with CYP121 of *M. tuberculosis* and minimum match with Cytochrome P450 Svu016 of *Streptomyces virginiae* that had maximum identity of 33% (Total score, 159). No Human cytochrome showed similarity with 2ij7. Structure of these targets was downloaded as PDB files from protein data bank [<http://www.rcsb.org/pdb/home/home.do>]. Active site identification was done using EXOME Horizon interface (http://mgl.com/life_sciences_exome_horizon.html).

We have carried out active site analysis of known three dimensional structures with complex form Cytochromes (CYP51, CYP121, CYP124, CYP125, CYP130 and CYP142) of using EXOME Horizon by following step. First we have downloaded three dimensional structure of Cytochromes P450 with complex from Protein data bank. We have done active site analysis by uploading the receptor PDB file on EXOME Horizon.

After completion of identifying target, validating a target, finding three dimensional structure of target and then using their structural information we searched a new compound as a drug similar to azole compound and took lead like molecule from ZINC database^{34,35}. From the table of ZINC database we downloaded 0, 1, 2 slices. Discovery Studio 4.0 and Autodock 4³⁶ were used for docking program. The receptor molecule is the CYP121 (PDB id 2ij7) and all the molecules obtained from the clustering process were used as ligand molecules. The molecules with the binding energy better than the natural docked molecule are reported for further analysis. The three dimensional (3D) structures of the ligands which were essential for docking were drawn using chemsketch. The ligands were then analyzed for drug-relevant properties based on Lipinski's rule of five and Dr. Arup K Ghose's modified 'Lipinski's rule of five'^{37,38}. QSAR is also done for 180 molecules. Finally filtration was done for evaluation of druglikeness of the target molecules by ADMET properties³⁹.

Protein-ligand docking :

The docking of ligands to the Cytochrome P450 protein for Tuberculosis was performed using Auto Dock Vina software. Auto Dock Vina significantly improves the average accuracy of the binding mode predictions compared to Auto Dock 4⁴⁰. Protein preparation and ligand preparation were done by Discovery studio 4.0. After docking results were visualized by Discovery studio 4.0 on Intel core i5 processor and 8 GB DDR3 R.A.M Computer.

Results and discussion

Computation :

The structural analogous of fluconazole has been designed from different chemical nuclei using ZINC database and EXOME HORIZON (Table 1). The selected molecules are similar with SMILES structure of fluconazole. A total of 55865 molecules have been obtained as hits, i.e. the molecules with similar structure to fluconazole. In next step ADMET filtering has been done for removal of toxic molecule from the list of molecules. For combinatorial library designing of druglike ligand Lipinski's rule of five is used. By using this rule 10,000 molecules have been filtered for druglikeness. Then ADMET filtering is done to remove toxic compounds, after that 4000 molecules are obtained which are similar to fluconazole and taken as lead molecules for further analysis. The docking score analyses (-7.7 to -9.9) suggest that 20 molecules are comparable with fluconazole (-8.0) and passed Lipinski's rule of five (Supplementary Material Table SF2). Docking score quantitatively predicts the strength of non-covalent interaction in a particular pose by counting the number of favorable intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonds, X-H... π , π ... π interactions and hydrophobic contacts between protein structure and the drug molecule after they have been docked. So more negative the docking score refers to more stable interaction. Following the Lipinski's and Ghose's rules those include docking score, log P data, molecular weight, number of hydrogen bond donors or acceptors, number of rotatable bonds, polar surface area, molar re-

fractivity etc. the druglikeness of the target molecule is predicted. The log P determines preferential lipophilicity of the compound in octanol versus water. Increase in log P suggests the increase in binding to receptor/enzyme, absorption through membrane and decreases aqueous solubility.

Interaction analysis of N-((6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]azepin-3-yl)methyl)naphthalen-2-amine (h) :

N-((6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-5H-[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]azepin-3-yl)methyl)naphthalen-2-amine (g) (Zinc database id : ZINC03885566; Pubchem id : CID 3744940 provided by <http://www.enamine.net> id Z87001561) has structural similarity with some of 1-alkyl-2-{(7-imidophenyl)arylazo}imidazoles (a) and 1-alkyl-2-{(7-imidophenyl)naphthyl- α/β -azo}imidazoles (b-g) (Scheme 2) andazole drugs have potent anti-TB activity so we have analyzed interaction detail of this ligand (h) with CYPs and then compared it with total 180 arylazoimidazole derivatives those we have designed by variation of substituent. Docking score and log P values are given in Supplementary Material (SF-2).

Best dock score is calculated with CYP121 out of available six PDB structures of CYPs. Binding affinity changes with the change in substituents in imidazolyl and in aryl rings. Compounds derived from naphthalene ring shows higher binding affinity than the compounds derived from benzene ring. In general compounds contain nitro (-NO₂) or chloro (-Cl) groups show better docking score. Methyl, ethyl or benzyl substituted imidazole derivatives binds more tightly with CYP121 compared to unsubstituted imidazolyl derivatives. So binding affinity increases with the steric effect in imidazolyl ring, i.e. ethyl substituted imidazolyl derivatives have better docking score than methyl substituted derivatives. Benzyl substituted ligands even exhibit better affinity towards the protein, but few benzyl substituted compounds exceeds the log P limit according to Lipinski's rule of five due to increase in hydrophobic moiety (Supplementary Material Tables SF-3 to SF-8).

Table 1. Docking score and log P data following Lipinski's rule of five of 20 conventional molecules those exhibit analogues of TB drugs

Molecular Id. No.	Structure	IUPAC name	Docking score	log P
1.		2-Amino-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-5-oxo-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-4 <i>H</i> -chromene-3-carbonitrile	-8.9	0.799
2.		6-Methoxy-3-(4-methylbenzoyl)quinolin-4(1 <i>H</i>)-one	-9.4	1.966
3.		<i>N</i> -((6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-5 <i>H</i> -[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3- <i>a</i>]azepin-3-yl)methyl)naphthalen-2-amine	-9.3	4.135
4.		(13 <i>R</i> ,14 <i>R</i>)-Dodecahydro-10,13-dimethyl-2 <i>H</i> -cyclopenta[<i>a</i>]phenanthrene-3,16(4 <i>H</i> ,9 <i>H</i>)-dione	-9.7	2.822
5.		(9 <i>R</i> ,10 <i>S</i> ,11 <i>S</i> ,15 <i>R</i>)-13-(Hydroxymethyl)-11,15-dihydro-9 <i>H</i> -9,10-[3,4]epipyrroloanthracene-12,14(10 <i>H</i> ,13 <i>H</i>)-dione	-9.8	1.338
6.		(13 <i>R</i>)-17-Hydroxy-10,13-dimethyl-6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-1 <i>H</i> -cyclopenta[<i>a</i>]phenanthren-3(2 <i>H</i>)-one	-9.8	2.628
7.		7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-Decahydro-13-methyl-6 <i>H</i> -cyclopenta[<i>a</i>]phenanthrene-3,17-diol	-8.9	3.414

Table-1 (contd.)

8.		2,3-Dimethoxy-12-methyl-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':4,5]benzo[1,2-c]phenanthridin-12-ium	-9.3	3.835
9.		2-Allyl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydro-1,6,6-trimethyl-8-oxo-3-thioxonaphthalene-2-carbonitrile	-9.3	2.222
10.		7,8,9,11,12,13,15,16-Octahydro-10,13-dimethyl-6H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3,17(10H,14H)-dione	-9.6	1.982
11.		3,4,6,7-Tetrahydro-9-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-10-methylacridine-1,8(2H,5H,9H,10H)-dione	-9.6	2.001
12.		11-Acetyl-8,10,10a,11-tetrahydro-6aH-8,10-epoxypyrano[4',3':3,4]pyrrolo[1,2-a]quinolin-7(6bH)-one	-8.6	-0.415
13.		1-Phenyl-2-(4-phenylpiperazin-1-yl)ethanol	-8.6	2.583
14.		2,3,4,4a-Tetrahydro-2,3,4,8,10-pentahydroxy-9-methoxy-1H-benzo[c]chromen-6(10bH)-one	-7.7	-1.079

Table-1 (contd.)

15.		3-Methoxy-10-methyl-4a,5,6,9,10,11-hexahydrobenzofuro[3,2-de]isoquinolin-6-ol	-8.9	1.147
16.		2-((2-Oxo-2-(p-tolylamino)ethyl)thio)-N-phenylacetamide	-8.5	2.960
17.		1-((4S,6aR)-4-Hydroxy-6a,8a-dimethyl-3,4,5,6,6a,6b,7,8,8a,8b,9a,10,10a,10b-tetradecahydro-1H-naphtho[2',1':4,5]indeno[1,2-b]oxiren-8b-yl)ethanone	-9.8	1.900
18.		1-(4-Hydroxy-6a,8a-dimethylhexadecahydro-1H-naphtho[2',1':4,5]indeno[1,2-b]oxiren-8b-yl)ethanone	-9.5	2.510
19.		1-(1-(1H-Indol-3-yl)isoquinolin-2(1H)-yl)ethanone	-9.9	3.287
20.		2-(2,4-Difluorophenyl)-1,3-di(1H-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-2-ol (Fluconazole)	-8.0	0.333

The molecular-ID-85 contains a coumarin moiety and has highest docking score with very good ADMET data (Tables 2, 4). There are total 12 amino acid residue near the best docked pose of molecular-Id-85 (Met86, Thr77, Asn85, Ala75, Val78, Phe168) and it forms five hydrogen (4 conventional hydrogen bonds) with Met86, Thr77,

Asn85 and two π - π interactions (π - σ and π - π stacked) with Val78 and Phe168. Details are given in Supplementary file SF-6. Keto group of coumarin moiety forms H-bond with Met86 (2.91 Å) and Asn85 (3.20 Å), nitrogen atom of oxazole moiety forms H-bond with Thr77 (3.11 Å) and aromatic ring forms π -bond with Phe168 (3.93

Table 2. Best five drug like molecules with reference to docking score

No.	Structure	Docking score (kcal/mol)	Drug likeness properties	ADMET PASSED
60b	<p>(<i>E</i>)-1-((1-Benzyl-1<i>H</i>-imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)-<i>N</i>-(3-nitrophenyl)-naphthalen-2-amine</p>	-12.5	*Lipinski's rule of five Molecular weight (≤ 500).....: 449.4839 Daltons -> Ok Number of HB acceptors (≤ 10)...: 5 -> Ok Number of HB donors (≤ 5).....: 2 -> Ok Virtual log P (≤ 5).....: 4.857 -> Ok Lipinski's rule of five.....: Ok *Ghose's rule Molecular weight (160 -> 480)....: 449.4839 Daltons -> Ok Number of atoms (20 -> 70).....: 55 -> Ok Virtual log P (-0.4 -> 5.6).....: 4.857 -> Ok Molar refractivity (40 -> 130)...: 130.9357 -> No Ghose's rule.....: No	NO
60c	<p>(<i>E</i>)-1-((1-Benzyl-1<i>H</i>-imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)-<i>N</i>-(4-nitrophenyl)-naphthalen-2-amine</p>	-12.4	*Lipinski's rule of five Molecular weight (≤ 500).....: 449.4839 Daltons -> Ok Number of HB acceptors (≤ 10)...: 5 -> Ok Number of HB donors (≤ 5).....: 2 -> Ok Virtual log P (≤ 5).....: 4.249 -> Ok Lipinski's rule of five.....: Ok *Ghose's rule Molecular weight (160 -> 480)....: 449.4839 Daltons -> Ok Number of atoms (20 -> 70).....: 55 -> Ok Virtual log P (-0.4 -> 5.6).....: 4.249 -> Ok Molar refractivity (40 -> 130)...: 130.9357 -> No Ghose's rule.....: No	NO
68c	<p>(<i>E</i>)-4-((1-Benzyl-1<i>H</i>-imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)-<i>N</i>-(4-formylphenyl)-naphthalen-2-amine</p>	-12.1	*Lipinski's rule of five Molecular weight (≤ 500).....: 431.4886 Daltons -> Ok Number of HB acceptors (≤ 10)...: 4 -> Ok Number of HB donors (≤ 5).....: 1 -> Ok Virtual log P (≤ 5).....: 4.900 -> Ok Lipinski's rule of five.....: Ok *Ghose's rule	NO

Table-2 (contd.)

yl)diazenyl)naphthalen-2-yl)amino)-benzaldehyde	Molecular weight (160 -> 480)....: 431.4886 Daltons -> Ok Number of atoms (20 -> 70).....: 54 -> Ok Virtual log P (-0.4 -> 5.6).....: 4.900 -> Ok Molar refractivity (40 -> 130)...: 130.4338 -> No	
48a	-12.0	NO
	*Ghose's rule.....: No *Lipinski's rule of five Molecular weight (<= 500).....: 417.5050 Daltons -> Ok Number of HB acceptors (<= 10)..: 3 -> Ok Number of HB donors (<= 5).....: 1 -> Ok Virtual log P (<= 5).....: 6.452 -> No Lipinski's rule of five.....: No	
(E)-1-((1-Benzyl-1H-imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)-N-(o-tolyl)naphthalen-2-amine	*Ghose's rule Molecular weight (160 -> 480)....: 417.5050 Daltons -> Ok Number of atoms (20 -> 70).....: 55 -> Ok Virtual log P (-0.4 -> 5.6).....: 6.452 -> No Molar refractivity (40 -> 130)...: 129.3372 -> Ok	
85	-11.6	YES
	*Ghose's rule.....: No *Lipinski's rule of five Molecular weight (<= 500).....: 381.3868 Daltons -> Ok Number of HB acceptors (<= 10)..: 5 -> Ok Number of HB donors (<= 5).....: 2 -> Ok Virtual log P (<= 5).....: 3.891 -> Ok Lipinski's rule of five.....: Ok	
(E)-6-((3-((1H-Imidazol-2-yl)diazenyl)naphthalen-2-yl)amino)-2H-chromen-2-one	*Ghose's rule Molecular weight (160 -> 480)....: 381.3868 Daltons -> Ok Number of atoms (20 -> 70).....: 44 -> Ok Virtual log P (-0.4 -> 5.6).....: 3.891 -> Ok Molar refractivity (40 -> 130)...: 110.2101 -> Ok Ghose's rule.....: Ok	

Å). Naphthyl moiety also forms π -bond but bond distances is more than 4 Å.

Ramachandran plot :

A Ramachandran plot⁴¹ generated from of *M. tuberculosis*-CYP121 in complex with the antifungal drug fluconazole that contains both β -sheet and α -helix (PDB ID 2ij7 A chain). The magenta, sky blue, regions represent the favored, allowed, and "generously allowed" regions and small green molecules represents amino acids as defined by Discovery studio 4.0 and Procheck⁴². An idea of secondary structure of protein can gain from the plot which has shown that the secondary structure of CYP121 has not changed after making in as receptor even docking, the 3d structure of the protein remains unperturbed. This suggests that the ligand bound to its active site (Supplementary Material SF-9).

Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) (MLR) :

QSAR is used for quantitative correlation of physico-chemical attributes of ligands. It has transformed into an extensively used tool, significantly contributing to the drug discovery process. Multiple Linear Regression is used as a chemo-metric method for variable selection and statistical fitting. MLR takes a group of random variables and tries to find a mathematical association among them. We observed MLR of 180 molecules (structure analogues) (Supplementary Materials SF-10). We took druglikeness properties (Molecular weight, hydrogen acceptor, hydrogen donor and log P) of these molecules as independent variable and docking score as dependent variable for MLR. Open office used for MLR calculation. The MLR result showed that R value is 0.828 and R^2 is 0.686. The values

Table 3. Docking score and log P of drugs used in TB treatment

Drugs	Structure	Docking score
Ethambutanol (1st line drug)		-5.2
Amikacin (2nd line drug)		-9.0
Bedaquiline (3rd line drug)		-8.6

Fig. 3. Comprehensive perception of CYP121 and ligand (g) (reference molecule)-interaction after docking. (a) Ligand is docked in active site of CYP121. Secondary structure of CYP121 represented by solid ribbon model, coiled ribbons represents alpha helix, flat structures represents beta sheet and thin connecting lines represents loop. Ligand and Hem represented by ball and stick. Hem is coloured according to element and ligand is highlighted in yellow colour. (b) Interactions of ligand with CYP121 amino acids omitting CYP121, the interaction type and bond distances. Classic hydrogen bonds are in green. Hydrophobic (π -alkyl) bonds are in light pink. Hydrophobic (π - σ) are in purple. Other bond (π -S) is in orange and (π - π) bonds are in orange and purple combined continuous lines. Ligand surrounding amino acids are in three letters code represented in blue. (c) Same picture represented in 2 dimension format. Details of ligand protein is given in Supplementary Material Tables SF-3 and SF-4.

Fig. 4. Comprehensive perception of CYP121 and ligand 156 interaction after docking. (a) Ligand is docked in active site of CYP121. Secondary structure of CYP121 represented by solid ribbon model, coiled ribbons represents alpha helix, flat structures represents beta sheet and thin connecting lines represents loop. Ligand and Hem represented by ball and stick. Hem is coloured according to element and ligand is highlighted in yellow colour. (b) Interactions of ligand with CYP121 amino acids omitting CYP121, the interaction type and bond distances. Classic hydrogen bonds are in dark green. Carbon Hydrogen Bond is in light green. Hydrophobic (π -alkyl) are in light pink. Hydrophobic (π - σ) is in purple. Hydrophobic bonds (π -alkyl) are in light pink. π - π T-shaped bonds are in dark pink and π - π stacked are in purple combined continuous lines. Ligand surrounding amino acids are in three letters code represented in blue. (c) Same picture represented in 2 dimension format. Details of ligand protein is in Supplementary Materials SF-5 and SF-6.

Fig. 5. Comprehensive perception of CYP121 and ligand fluconazole interaction after docking. (a) Ligand is docked in active site of CYP121. Secondary structure of CYP121 represented by solid ribbon model, coiled ribbons represents alpha helix, flat structures represents beta sheet and thin connecting lines represents loop. Ligand and Hem represented by ball and stick. Hem is coloured according to element and ligand is highlighted in yellow colour. (b) Interactions of ligand with CYP121 amino acids omitting CYP121, the interaction type and bond distances. Classic hydrogen bonds are in dark green. Hydrophobic (pi-pi t-shaped) is in dark pink. Hydrophobic bonds (pi-alkyl) are in light pink pi cations are in orange. Ligand surrounding amino acids are in three letters code represented in blue. (c) Same picture represented in 2 dimension format. Details of ligand protein is in Supplementary Material SF-7 and SF-8.

Fig. 6. Ramachandran plot of CYP121 (PDB ID : 2ij7 A chain). (a) *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* CYP121 in complex with the antifungal drug fluconazole that contains both β -sheet and α -helix (PDB ID 2ij7 A chain). Protein data bank file's amino acids are in ϕ (phi) and ψ (psi) angle coordinate. (b) No changes in the amino acid positions after making it receptor. The magenta, sky blue, regions represent the favored, allowed, and "generously allowed" regions and small green molecules represents amino.

Table 4. The ADME calculated data of ((*E*)-6-((3-((1*H*-imidazol-2-yl)diazonyl)-4,4*a*-dihydronaphthalen-2-yl)amino)-2*H*-chromen-2-one (Id-156, vide SF-2)

Property	Value	Probability
Human Intestinal Absorption	+	1.0000
Blood-Brain Barrier	+	0.9168
Caco-2 Permeability	+	0.5080
<i>p</i> -Glycoprotein Substrate	Non-substrate	0.6562
<i>p</i> -Glycoprotein Inhibitor I	Non-inhibitor	0.6357
<i>p</i> -Glycoprotein Inhibitor II	Non-inhibitor	0.7634
Renal Organic Cation Transporter	Non-inhibitor	0.7057
CYP450 2C9 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.8940
CYP450 2D6 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.8343
CYP450 3A4 Substrate	Non-substrate	0.5911
CYP450 1A2 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.8793
CYP450 2C9 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.6522
CYP450 2D6 Inhibitor	Inhibitor	0.5516
CYP450 2C19 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.5075
CYP450 3A4 Inhibitor	Non-inhibitor	0.7216
CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	High CYP Inhibitory Promiscuity	0.5350
Ames Toxicity	Non AMES toxic	0.5502
Carcinogenicity	Non-carcinogens	0.9017
Biodegradation	Not ready biodegradable	0.9879
Rat Acute Toxicity	2.6251 LD ₅₀ , mol/kg	Not applicable
hERG inhibition (predictor I)	Weak inhibitor	0.6238
hERG inhibition (predictor II)	Non-inhibitor	0.9213

of R and R^2 are close to +1, and so implies positive and good correlation between druglikeness and docking score⁴³. 68.6% of the change can be explained by the change in the 4 independent variables. We could assume that docking score is changing along with druglikeness properties. For detail result see supplementary file (Supplementary Material SF-10).

ADMET property analysis :

Screening and enhancing ADMET attributes in the early stage of the drug design process are widely accepted nowadays⁴⁴. Traditional approaches tried to create certain associations among molecular properties and ADMET properties using statistical methods or machine learning algorithms⁴⁵. Among them, support vector ma-

chine (SVM) is a superior method which has been also widely applied in the drug discovery methods recently⁴⁶. ADMET can predict permeability for Caco-2 cell, BBB (blood-brain barrier), HIA (human intestinal absorption), P-glycoprotein Substrate/Inhibitor, renal organic cation Transporter, etc. ADMET result shows 156 are positive (+) in Human Intestinal Absorption, Blood-Brain Barrier and Caco-2 Permeability which means the molecule is well absorbed in human body (Table 4). Inhibition and initiation of P-glycoprotein have been reported as the causes of drug-drug interactions⁴⁷. 156 is P-glycoprotein non-inhibitor, in the result, that means 156 won't interact with other drugs. Data in Table 4 shows best fitted ligand is in permissible limit.

Organic cation transporters are responsible for drug absorption and disposition in the kidney, liver, and intestine⁴⁸. ADMET result of Id-156 is Non-inhibitor of renal organic cation transporter that means Id-156 will be well absorbed in kidney, liver, and intestine.

The human Cytochromes P450 (CYPs), particularly isoforms 1A2, 2C9, 2C19, 2D6, and 3A4, are responsible for about 90% oxidative metabolic reactions. Inhibition of CYP enzymes will lead to inductive or inhibitory failure of drug metabolism⁴⁹. ADMET result shows 156 is Non-inhibitor of the Cytochromes P450 (CYPs).

The Ames test is a widely employed method that uses bacteria to test whether a given chemical can cause cancer. More formally, it is a biological assay to assess the mutagenic potential of chemical compounds^{50,51}. ADMET result shows 156 are non-ames toxic and non-carcinogenic.

hERG is a gene sensitive to drug binding⁵². ADMET result shows 156 Weak inhibitor and Non-inhibitor of hERG inhibition (predictor I and II). That means 156 will be well bind with receptor. Detail results are given in Supplementary Material SF-11.

Conclusion

In this study we have successfully considered that arylazoimidazole derivatives showed better binding affinity than fluconazole to CYP121 and may serve good

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model drug to *M. tuberculosis*. The most of the ligands were passed through ADMET and drug like properties filtration successfully, so arylazoimidazole derivatives have potential of being a good drug.

Supplementary materials

Full BLAST analysis (SF-1), docking score and druglikeness (SF-2), interaction analysis (SF-3-SF-8), Ramachandran plot (SF-9), QSAR table (SF-10), ADMET tables are given (SF-11).

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List of abbreviations

MTB : *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

CYP : Cytochrome P450s

PDB : Protein Data Bank

BLAST : Basic Local Alignment Search Tool

MIC : Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

QSAR : Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

MLR : Multiple Linear Regression

LD₅₀ : Half concentration of Lethal dose

ADMET : Absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, toxicity

hERG : Human *Ether-à-go-go*-Related Gene

Id-156 : (*E*)-6-((3-((1*H*-Imidazol-2-yl)diazanyl)-naphthalen-2-yl)amino)-2*H*-chromen-2-one

References

1. WHO Guidelines Approved by the Guidelines Review Committee : World Health Organization, 2010.
2. R. P. Tripathi, N. Tewari, N. Dwivedi and V. K. Tiwari, *Med. Res. Rev.*, 2005, **25**, 93.
3. S. A. Hudson, K. J. McLean, A. W. Munro and C. Abell, *Biochem. Soc. Trans.*, 2012, **40**, 573.
4. A. Zumla, P. Nahid and S. T. Cole, *Nature Rev. Drug Disc.*, 2013, **12**, 388.
5. K. J. McLean, K. R. Marshall, A. Richmond, I. S. Hunter, K. Fowler and T. Kieser, *Microbiology*, 2002, **148**, 2937.
6. H. Ouellet, L. M. Podust and P. R. de Montellano, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2008, **283**, 5069.
7. A. W. Munro, K. J. McLean, K. R. Marshall, A. J. Warman, G. Lewis and O. Roitel, *Biochem. Soc. Trans.*, 2003, **31**, 625.
8. K. J. McLean, P. Carroll, D. G. Lewis, A. J. Dunford, H. E. Seward and R. Neeli, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2008, **283**, 33406.
9. H. E. Seward, A. Roujeinikova, K. J. McLean, A. W. Munro and D. Leys, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2006, **281**, 39437.
10. E. V. Granowitz and R. B. Brown, *Critical Care Clinics*, 2008, **24**, 421.
11. E. Merino, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 3835.
12. J. E. Lesch, Oxford University Press, 2007, **1**.
13. F. Carey and R. Giuliano, McGraw-Hill Education, 2013, **8**.
14. H. Xu and X. Zeng, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **20**, 4193.
15. M. Tonelli, I. Vazzana, B. Tasso, V. Boido, F. Sparatore and M. Fermeglia, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 4425.
16. G. K. Rauth, S. Pal, D. Das, C. Sinha, A. M. Z. Slawin and J. D. Woollins, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 363.
17. R. Roy, P. Chattopadhyay, C. Sinha and S. Chattopadhyay, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 3361.
18. T. Mathur, U. S. Ray, J. C. Liou, J. S. Wu, T. H. Lu and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 739.
19. P. Datta, D. Mallick, T. K. Mondal and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2014, **71**, 47.
20. J. Dinda, U. Ray, G. Mostafa, T. H. Lu, A. Usman, I. A. Razak, S. Chantrapromma, H. K. Fun and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 247.
21. T. K. Misra, D. Das, C. Sinha, P. Ghosh and C. K. Pal, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **37**, 1672.
22. U. Ray, S. Jasimuddin, B. K. Ghosh, M. Monfort, J. Ribas, G. Mostafa, T. H. Lu and C. Sinha, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **2**, 250.
23. S. Pal, D. Das, C. Sinha and C. H. L. Kennard, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **313**, 21.
24. P. Gayen, K. K. Sarker and C. Sinha, *Colloids and Surfaces (A)*, 2013, **429**, 60.
25. A. Nandi, C. Sen, S. Roy, D. Mallick, R. Sinha, T. K. Mondal and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2014, **79**, 186.
26. D. Sardar, P. Datta, S. Das, B. Saha, S. Samanta, D. Bhattacharya, P. Karmakar and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2013, **394**, 98.
27. P. Datta, A. P. Mukhopadhyay, E. R. T. Tiekink, P.

- Manna, P. C. Sil and C. Sinha, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2011, **105**, 577.
28. M. K. Paira, T. K. Mondal, D. Ojha, A. M. Z. Slawin, J. Derek Woollins, E. Tiekink, A. Samanta and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **370**, 175.
29. J. Dinda, D. Das, P. K. Santra, C. Sinha and L. R. Falvello, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2001, **629**, 28.
30. B. K. Santra and G. K. Lahiri, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1998, **10**, 1613.
31. P. Pratihar, T. K. Mondal, P. Raghavaiah and C. Sinha, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 831.
32. F. Ooms, *Cur. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **7**, 141.
33. H. Ouellet, J. B. Johnston and P. R. Ortiz de Montellano, *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*, 2010, **493**, 82.
34. S. F. Altschul, W. Gish, W. Miller, E. W. Myers and D. J. Lipman, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1990, **215**, 403.
35. J. D. Thompson, D. G. Higgins and T. J. Gibson, *Nucleic Acids Research*, 1994, **22**, 4673.
36. J. J. Irwin and B. K. Shoichet, *J. Chem. Inform. Mod.*, 2005, **45**, 77.
37. O. Trott and A. J. Olson, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2010, **31**, 455.
38. C. A. Lipinski, F. Lombardo, B. W. Dominy and P. J. Feeney, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*, 2001, **46**, 3.
39. A. K. Ghose, V. N. Viswanadhan and J. J. Wendoloski, *J. Combinat. Chem.*, 1999, **1**, 55.
40. J. Shen, F. Cheng, Y. Xu, W. Li and Y. Tang, *J. Chem. Inform. Model*, 2010, **50**, 1034.
41. G. M. Morris, R. Huey, W. Lindstrom, M. F. Sanner, R. K. Belew, D. S. Goodsell and A. J. Olson, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2009, **30**, 2785.
42. G. N. Ramachandran, C. Ramakrishnan and V. Sasisekharan, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1963, **7**, 959.
43. R. A. Laskowski, M. W. Macarthur, D. S. Moss and J. M. Thornton, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 1993, **26**, 283.
44. J. W. Creswell, SAGE Publications, 2003, **2**.
45. T. Hou and J. Wang, *Expert Opinion on Drug Metabolism & Toxicology*, 2008, **4**, 759.
46. Y. Sakiyama, *Expert Opinion on Drug Metabolism & Toxicology*, 2009, **5**, 149.
47. I. Kola and J. Landis, *Nature Rev. Drug Disc.*, 2004, **3**, 711.
48. J. H. Lin and M. Yamazaki, *Clinic. Pharmacol.*, 2003, **42**, 59.
49. L. Zhang, C. M. Brett and K. M. Giacomini, *Ann. Rev. Pharma. Tox.*, 1998, **38**, 431.
50. V. Uttamsingh, C. Lu, G. Miwa and L. S. Gan, *Drug Met. Dispo.*, 2005, **33**, 1723.
51. B. N. Ames, E. G. Gurney, J. A. Miller and H. Bartsch, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (USA)*, 1972, **69**, 3128.
52. K. Mortelmans and E. Zeiger, *Mut. Res.*, 2000, **455**, 29.
53. M. C. Sanguinetti and M. Tristani-Firouzi, *Nature*, 2006, **440**, 463.